

Chersina angulata

Angulate tortoise

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Reptile

Size: 22 cm maximum (total body length)

Distribution:

Western and Southern coastal areas of South Africa

Importance:

The angulate tortoise (*Chersina angulata*) is an endemic keystone herbivore of South Africa's Cape region, shaping vegetation structure and seed dispersal in the Cape Floristic Region. Its sequenced genome will support conservation genomics, clarify population structure and local adaptation, inform responses to climate change, and improve phylogenetic resolution within the tortoise family for effective long-term management.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 36.6 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 7.34 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 2.37 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 90.2% [Single: 83.1%, Duplicated: 7.1%]

BUSCO database: eukaryota

Assembly N50: 100.98 kilobases

Contig number: 37 324

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